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Research Article

**TO DETERMINE THE PERCEPTION ABOUT THE FACTORS
RELATED WITH POLY CYSTICOVARIAN SYNDROME (PCOS)
AMONG FEMALE MEDICAL AND NURSING STUDENTS****¹Dr Sadiq Jan**¹MBBS FCPS Assistant Professor, Obstetrics and Gynecology Islamic International Medical college Rawalpindi.**Article Received:** July 2019**Accepted:** August 2019**Published:** September 2019

Abstract: *To assess the perception about the factors associated with Poly Cystic Ovarian syndrome (PCOS), its health implication and preventive measures in medical and nursing student of Fatima Memorial College of medicine & dentistry, and Saeeda Waheed College of nursing, Lahore.*

Polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) is a multi-organ endocrine disease manifesting classically as hyper-androgenic, polycystic ovaries and an-ovulatory menstrual cycles affecting women of reproductive age world-wide^{1,2}. It was first described by Stein and Leventhal in 1935, since then it became a major health issue and has a world- wide prevalence of 6-10% among women in reproductive age². The reported prevalence is higher in Asian Pakistani women ranging up-to 52% as compared to white women which show a statistic of 10-20% and same is depicted by women in United Kingdom²

Study place: *Fatima Memorial College of medicine & dentistry, and Saeeda Waheed College of nursing, Lahore.*

Study duration: *The study was completed in 6 months duration, from October 2018 to March, 2019.*

Keywords: *Poly Cystic Ovarian syndrome, an-ovulatory, menstrual cycles.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) is a multi-organ endocrine disease manifesting classically as hyper-androgenic, polycystic ovaries and an-ovulatory menstrual cycles affecting women of reproductive age world-wide [1,2]. It was first described by Stein and Leventhal in 1935, since then it became a major health issue and has a world- wide prevalence of 6-10% among women in reproductive age [2]. The reported prevalence is higher in Asian Pakistani women ranging up-to 52% as compared to white women which show a statistic of 10-20% and same is depicted by women in United Kingdom [2]. Poly cystic ovarian syndrome is considered as complex syndrome comprising of metabolic, cardiovascular, reproductive, cosmetic and psychological manifestations [3,4]. Clinical features are obesity, insulin resistance, hyperinsulinemia, and type 2 diabetes mellitus, hypertension, dyslipidemia, anxiety, depression, hirsutism, alopecia, acne, abnormal menstruation, infertility, repeated miscarriage and increased risk of endometrial, ovarian and breast cancers [5,6]. Although, the main underlying cause is still unknown but genetic predisposition, excess androgen levels/sensitivity and deranged glucose metabolism due to insulin resistance seem to be the major contributors to the pathology of PCOS [7]. Due to wide array of symptoms and changing definition of PCOS, more than 70% of the women in community remains undiagnosed [8,9]. The Rotterdam criteria are the most widely accepted evidenced based criteria for the diagnosis across Europe, Asia and Australia. This criterion incorporates the National Institute of Health definition, which generally describes that If women fulfils any two of the three of Rotterdam criteria is confirmed to have PCOS [10]. The criteria include, oligo/anovulation, hyperandrogenism, and poly cystic ovaries on ultrasonography [11]. Based on the correct identification of sign and symptoms of this disease, management strategies can be identified [12]. The main focus of management and preventive measures is to minimize the risk of infertility, emotional stress so that the at-risk women can be protected against the future health problems¹². The foremost step should be early diagnosis of the disease and subsequent treatment [12]. The most significant strategies can be lifestyle modifications such as regular physical activity, dietary modifications (organic, low fat and low glycemic index foods), maintaining an optimal weight, controlling blood sugar levels, treatment of hormonal imbalance, stress management and having a strong social support system [12,13]. This can only be achieved by creating awareness among women [13]. The rationale of the current study is to assess the perception of the factors associated with PCOS,

its health-related problems and its preventive strategies among female medical and nursing students. It will be step to assess their awareness and at the same time will sensitize them about the PCOS so that they can play their role in creating health awareness about this growing health issue.

Objective: To assess the perception about the factors associated with Poly Cystic Ovarian syndrome (PCOS), its health implication and preventive measures in medical and nursing student of FMH college of Medicine and Dentistry.

METHODOLOGY:**Study design:**

It was a cross sectional study.

Study population:

Female MBBS and nursing students of Fatima Memorial College of Medicine and Dentistry and Saeeda Waheed college of Nursing.

Inclusion criteria:

1. The female MBBS and nursing students with age group between 19-24years
2. The female MBBS and nursing students who had given consent to participate in the study

Exclusion criteria:

1. The female MBBS and nursing students of age less than 19 years and more than 24years.
2. Male MBBS and nursing students.

Study place:

Fatima Memorial College of medicine & dentistry, and Saeeda Waheed College of nursing, Lahore.

Study duration:

The study was completed in 6 months duration, from Octobere 2018 to March, 2019.

Sampling technique:

Convenient sampling was used

Sample size:

Sample size was calculated keeping Z^2 at 95% Confidence level = 3.84 by keeping the prevalence at 20%. Absolute precision $d= 5\%$ (0.05) Minimal sample size required =250 (between the two groups) Formula used

$$n = Z^2 \frac{p(1-p)}{d^2}$$

Data collection procedure:

The data was collected from the FMC of Medicine and Dentistry MBBS and nursing students of Saeeda

-Waheed College of Nursing. The informed verbal consent was taken. The students were asked about their demographic profile and the perception of factors associated with PCOS, its health implication and preventive measures in a structured questionnaire. All students fulfilling criteria of the study gave an informed verbal consent and all those agreeing were included in the study, they were required to fill questionnaire.

Data analysis:

The completed questionnaires were entered in the computer software SPSS version 21. Means and standard deviations were calculated for quantitative variables like age. For categorical variables like question focusing the perception about different factors associated with PCOS, proportions and percentages were calculated. The level of significance was set at 95% ($p < 0.05$) and the power of the study at 80%.

Ethical considerations:

Approval for conducting the research was taken from Fatima Memorial Hospital (FMH) Institutional Review Board (IRB) . An Informed consent was

taken from all the participants. It was made sure by the investigator that the confidentiality of all the participants was maintained.

RESULTS:

Mean age of the respondents was 21.73 ± 1.11 SD for medical and 21.07 ± 2.22 SD for the nursing students (Table1). Academic year of the students varied from first to fifth year with majority of respondents for medical being from 4th year 71,(56.8%), while for nursing, the majority belonged to 2nd year, 72(57.6%). Of both the groups, majority 118 (94.4 %) medical, while 97 (76.4%) nursing students had prior knowledge of PCOS (Table 1). Moreover, majority from both the groups stated that most affected age group 16-35years (Table 1). Among 63 (50.4%) of medical and 68 (54.4%) of nursing students (Table 1) considered that estrogen hormone was raised in PCOS. Out of all, 114 (91.2%) medical and 103 (82.4%) nursing students had the knowledge about the association of polycystic ovaries with polycystic ovarian syndrome (Table 1). Almost of half of the medical and nursing students considered overweight and obesity as BMI category associated with PCOS.

(Table 1).

Table no 1: Knowledge about factors associated with PCOS

Response of Students	Medical Students 125(50%)		Nursing Students 125(50%)	
Knowledge about PCOS:				
Yes	118	94.4	97	77.6
No	7	5.6	28	22.4
Prevalent age group of females in PCOS:				
8-15 years	0	0	5	4
16-35 years	104	83.2	96	76.8
36-45 years	17	13.6	17	13.6
46-60 years	4	3.2	7	5.6
Hormones raised in PCOS:				
Estrogen Androgen Oxytocin Progesterone	63	50.4	68	54.4
	43	34.4	25	20
	8	6.4	6	4.8
	19	15.2	27	21.6
Association of Polycystic Ovaries with PCOS:				
Yes	114	91.2	103	82.4
	11	8.8	22	17.6
Association of BMI categories with PCOS:				
Normal Underweight Overweight Obese	16	12.8	10	8
	3	2.4	8	6.4
	70	56	54	43.2
	36	28.8	53	42.4
Association of irregular menstrual cycle with PCOS:				
Yes	116	92.8	113	90.4
	9	7.2	12	9.6

It was the opinion of 116 (92.8%) medical and 113 (90.4%) nursing students that irregular menstrual cycle was associated with PCOS (Table 1). Almost two third medical and nursing students considered polycystic ovaries as a criterion for diagnosis of polycystic ovarian syndrome (Table 1). Out of all interviewed, 92(73.6%) medical 79 (63.3%) of nursing students, had the perception that excessive facial hair is a symptom of PCOS. (Table 2). Infertility was agreed upon as a complication of

PCOS by 105 (84%) medical and 95 (76%) nursing students (Table 2). When perception about psychological events associated with polycystic ovarian syndrome were asked a majority of medical and nursing students thought depression and stress was most common event (Table 2). Maximum number of medical students 96 (76.8 %) and 79 (63.2 %) of nursing students perceived that obesity is a chronic disease that can be a result of polycystic ovarian disease.

(Table 2).

Table no 2: Knowledge about the conditions associated with PCOS

Response of Students	Medical Students 125 50%		Nursing Students 125 (50%)	
Signs and symptoms				
Excessive facial hair	92	73.6	79	63.2
Acne	63	50.4	12	9.6
Hair loss Rashes Migraine	20	16	10	8
	5	4	20	16
	8	6.4	6	4.8
Complications				
Abortions	18	14.4	10	8
Infertility	105	84	95	76
Breast/Ovarian/Uterine Cancer	25	20	17	13
Multiple Pregnancies	5	4	4	3.2
Psychological Events				
Mania Depression Anxiety	7	5.6	2	1.6
Schizophrenia Stress	72	57.6	47	37.6
	40	32	33	26.4
	3	2.4	5	4
	53	42.4	41	32.8
Chronic Disease				
Obesity	96	76.8	79	63.2
Chronic Liver disease	7	5.6	11	8.8
Diabetes	31	24.8	23	18.4
Hypertension	23	18.4	13	10.4

Ultrasound was chosen as the best method for early diagnosis of polycystic ovarian disease by 98 (78.4%) of medical students and 75(60%) of nursing students. (Table 3). Out of all the medical, 112 (89.6%) while 119 (95.2%) nursing students thought it is a treatable disease (Table 3). It was the opinion of 94 (75.2%) medical and 93 (74.4%) nursing students that gynecologist can give the best treatment for polycystic ovarian syndrome (Table 3). Out of all 83 (66.4%) medical and 49 (39.2%) nursing students believe that high cholesterol diet increases the risk of

polycystic ovarian syndrome (Table 3). Maximum of 81 (64.8%) medical and 48 (38.4%) nursing students believe that exercise (a lifestyle modification) can prevent PCOS (Table 3). Internet was considered as the best source for spreading awareness of polycystic ovarian syndrome by 81 (64.8%) medical students and 48 (38.4%) nursing students (Table 3).

Table no 3: Knowledge about the early diagnosis, treatment and prevention associated with PCOS

Response of Students	Medical student 125 (50%)		Nursing student 125 (50%)	
Methods of early diagnosis:				
Ultrasound	98	78.4	75	60
Liver function test Hormonal blood test Lipid profile	1	0.8	2	1.6
Glucose tolerance test	46	36.8	44	35.2
Kidney function test	11	8.8	2	1.6
	8	6.4	3	2.4
	2	1.6	0	0
Knowledge if PCOS is treatable:				
Yes	98	78.4	75	60
No	1	0.8	2	1.6
Polycystic ovaries a criterion for diagnosis of PCOS:				
Yes	80	64	94	75.2
No	45	36	31	24.8
Knowledge about specialty treating PCOS:				
Gynaecologist	94	75.2	93	74.4
-	3	2.4	3	2.4
General physician General surgeon Endocrinologist	2	1.6	2	1.6
	46	36.8	28	22.4
Diet which increase the risk of PCOS:				
High fibre diet	6	4.8	19	15.2
High carbohydrate diet	37	29.6	45	36
High protein diet	16	12.8	13	10.4
High cholesterol diet	83	66.4	49	39.2
Lifestyle modifications helping in prevention of PCOS:				
Exercise Diet control	81	64.8	48	38.4
Adequate sleep	65	52	35	28
Weight loss	8	6.4	8	6.4
	66	52.8	38	30.4
Best source for spreading awareness of PCOS:				
internet/social media	89	71.2	57	45.6
print media electronic media	19	15.2	1	8
focus group discussion seminars	32	25.6	17	13.6
workshops	19	15.2	8	6.4
	43	34.4	28	22.4
	18	14.4	20	16

DISCUSSION:

Polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) is a heterogeneous collection of signs and symptoms that when gathered, form a spectrum of disorder with disturbance of reproductive, endocrine, and metabolic functions [1]. It is the most prevalent of all the endocrine disorders affecting women of reproductive age and continues to rise rapidly worldwide [1]. Currently, it is the most debated topic due to various questions regarding its exact cause, diagnosis, prevention and treatment [2]. Despite the importance of the disease, it is still an unrecognized condition due to lack of awareness in people especially women [2]. PCOS targets the reproductive age group (15-49 years) mainly because it is the duration of life of a woman when hormones are regulated by menstrual cycle [3]. The majority students of both groups also perceived that most affected age group is 16-35 years (reproductive age) and thus the literature also states the same. [2] The Endocrine Society and 2003 Rotterdam PCOS consensus recommend that PCOS can be diagnosed if the adult women present with any two of the following features that is; excess production of androgens, anovulation and pearl sized cyst found in ovaries [4,5,10,11]. Majority of students in both discipline in current study perceived that, estrogen was the main hormone, while literature supports that the main cause of PCOS is hyperandrogenism, as stated by Androgen Excess Society (AES) "PCOS should be defined by presence of hyperandrogenism in combination with ovarian dysfunction" [3,11]. It was note-worthy that two third of the students correctly perceived that polycystic ovaries come under the diagnostic criteria of PCOS. Metabolic disturbances constitute an important part of PCOS with insulin resistance and obesity being an integral part [6]. Obesity and PCOS have a two-way relation [6,7,8]. On the contrary, PCOS may itself cause increase in weight [7]. This is of importance because a high MI can also lead to other chronic diseases like hypertension, and diabetes [8]. Majority of the students had an insight that women having $BMI \geq 24Kg/m^2$, were likely to develop PCOS as also supported by many studies [8]. However, exceptions were present as women with BMI within normal or less can also suffer from the same disease. Regarding chronic diseases, overall opinion of students was that PCOS results in obesity which is supported by certain studies that state obesity as well as diabetes can follow in PCOS patients [9,12,13]. Any disruption in menstrual cycle will lead to hormone imbalance and thus leading to PCOS. More than two third, of the female students of both disciplines were aware that irregular menstrual cycles were associated with PCOS as an alarming sign and one of the main causes of infertility in women.

Likewise, PCOS has also been reported as second most common cause of infertility and pathophysiology explains that hypersecretion of Luteinizing Hormone (LH), excessive androgen secretion, and developmental defects of follicles leads to anovulation are the root causes [11]. All students, unanimously agreed upon the fact that infertility is the common and most troublesome complication of PCOS. [10,11] Infertility is a rising worldwide problem. Pakistan is among the rapidly growing countries but still has high rate of infertility [7]. PCOS is troublesome not only because of the associated health issues but also due to cosmetic reasons. Symptoms like acne, excessive facial hair, hirsutism, seborrhea, androgenic alopecia, and various others are not very cosmetically appealing and is a source of concern in young girls [10]. Fasting insulin levels is the most common abnormality seen in both acne and hirsutism, whereas alopecia is associated with high testosterone levels. In the opinion of the interviewees, excessive facial hair is an early symptom and, acne is an early sign of PCOS. Hence, the studies suggest that the early symptoms of this syndrome can vary from woman to woman [11,12] Psychological effects such as anxiety and depression are pivotal features of PCOS that are associated with level of testosterone [12]. These often go unidentified. However, when students were asked, they agreed that depression and anxiety as the commonest psychological effect. Due to its remarkable effects on women life, early diagnosis and management as treatment is the key to counter this endocrine disorder [10]. Keeping in view the Rotterdam Criteria, pelvic ultrasound and hormone blood test should be assessed to see polycystic ovaries, ovulation status and androgen levels respectively to confirm the diagnosis [11]. Ultrasound was chosen as the best method for early diagnosis of the disease in our current study. It is not a completely curable disease and it can be managed through prompt treatment in which gynecologist and endocrinologists can play a vital role. Hormonal contraceptives for those who are not planning pregnancy whereas clomiphene citrate, anti-androgens, metformin for fertility¹³. PCOS has a strong association with quality of diet and lifestyle changes. The incidence has increased dramatically in recent years because of the intake of fast food, artificial sweeteners, soft drinks and juices [13]. Lack of exercise, sedentary lifestyle, adds fuel to the fire by further increasing the risk. When questioned about the diet which increases the risk of PCOS, majority agreed that high cholesterol diet is the main reason while a small percentage had the knowledge that high carbohydrate diet is one of high risk [12]. As far as the lifestyle modification is concerned, medical and

nursing students were on the same page choosing weight loss and exercise as the best option [13]. Hence, women should be educated to engage in regular exercise and adopt healthy lifestyle, as it significantly improves the condition and the best way of management. Moreover, there should be continuous monitoring of the women and comparison of the results before and after lifestyle changes as done by one of the studies [13].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that the knowledge about the different factors associated with PCOS, its health implications and prevention measures among the medical students was better as compared to nursing students. This study had been an important source of creating knowledge among nursing students. The Awareness can also be increased via real time patient encounter, social media and printed literature.

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